

Extremization of Fisher's Information, Free Particle and Conservation of Energy

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The extremization of Fisher's information subject to constraints usually containing $V(x)$, the classical potential, appears in the literature (1), (2). $V(x)$, however, is a concept introduced by Newton and associated with conservation of energy for a conservative potential. We argue the appearance of $V(x)$ in an extremization approach to obtain an "equation" bypasses the already existing conservation of energy equation. If $V(x)$ is used, we argue that one cannot dispense with conservation of energy and that it should be written a priori. If that is the case, what does extremization of Fisher's information guarantee?

In (1) a probability distribution $P(x)$ is set equal to $W(x)W(x)$ its square root. In (2), a complex function is defined: $W(x) = \sqrt{\text{density}(x)} \exp(i S/\hbar)$ where S is the classical action. Here $\text{density}(x)=P(x)$. In both cases, the square root of the density appears.

The problem, we argue, is that for a free particle with $\text{density}(x)=P(x)=1$, there is no Fisher's information to extremize, yet the free particle is a key part of quantum mechanics. Its probability (square root probability) is the solution of an eigenvalue problem of the translation operator $-i\hbar d/dx$ and it is consistent with Newtonian mechanics i.e. conservation of energy with $E = p^2/2m$. From this one may create an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The average kinetic energy is $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ which happens to be the extremized value of Fisher's information for $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$.

In other words, we argue that conservation of energy must occur and that one needs a solution for a free particle and this does not follow from Fisher's information extremization. Extremization of Fisher's information produces the form $d/dx dW/dx$ which is taken to be linked to $\langle p^2 \rangle$ which already follows from $-d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx)$.

One argument made in the literature (3) is that Newtonian conservation of energy also follows from Fisher's information extremization i.e. the Lagrangian for a free particle $\frac{1}{2}m dx/dt dx/dt$ is of the form of a Fisher's information with $xx = \text{probability}$ (which is unusual). The strategy, it seems, is that one may apply extremization of Fisher's information directly to a quantum problem by assuming a $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and use d/dx instead of $P=xx$ with d/dt . An issue, as noted, is that for a free particle $W(x)$ exists, but extremization of Fisher's information does not exist. Even if $E=p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistically) and this follows from the extremization of Fisher's information, $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ does not, but it is consistent with $E=p^2/2m$. The reason for this consistency is that it contains p (momentum) which by its very definition must ensure $E=p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistically). Fisher information extremization, however, yields the bound state solution i.e. may be used to derive the Schrodinger equation. In (1) this is done for a bound state, in (2) for the more general case, but (2) defines $W(x) = \sqrt{\text{density}} \exp(iS/\hbar)$ where $S =$ the classical action. For a free particle, the definition of $W(x)$ is $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which is the solution of the free particle problem without using any equation. Thus the definition is the solution itself for the free particle case in (2).

It seems that Fisher's information, which uses $\text{density}(x)$, does not include a scheme for describing motion in one direction in space without time present. $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ distributions in two dimensions allow for this. This motion is associated with the translation operator d/dx which we argue is key in solving for the square-root probability of a

free particle in keeping with $E=pp/2m$, which (3) argues follows from the extremization of Fisher's information. Thus, even if one accepts the argument that Fisher's information is responsible for the energy conservation equation, using Fisher's information = $\int dx/dt dx/dt$ constant, does that allow one to immediately switch to a problem with $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and the derivative d/dx and apply Fisher's extremization there, we ask? We argue that there is an implicit assumption that:

$$C1 dx/dt dx/dt = C2 d/dx dW/dx / W \text{ where } C1 \text{ and } C2 \text{ are constants}$$

This implies that for a free particle which treats each x point the same i.e. $P(x)=\text{constant}$, $W(x)W(x)$ cannot be $P(x)$. It also implies that $d/dx dW/dx = pp W$ ((1)) where $p=\text{mov}$ nonrelativistically. ((1)), however, is the solution to the free particle problem without performing any Fisher information extremization i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution. This solution may be used to create an ensemble $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which may be used in a conservation of average energy equation.

Thus we argue that Fisher extremization used to create the Schrodinger equation is based already on the idea that $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle and simply produces the conservation of energy equation which is already known to exist from Newtonian mechanics or Fisher's information extremization which is argued to be the same as Lagrangian variation in (3).

Extremization of the Lagrangian, Newtonian Mechanics and Fisher Extremization

We begin with the notion of conservation of energy which follows from Newtonian mechanics where $p=\text{mov}$ (nonrelativistically) represents an impulse which may be measured by noting the damage done to a target. (Thus this idea should carry over relativistically.)

Newtonian mechanics may be formulated using a Lagrangian (or Hamiltonian) scheme which involves an extremization process. In the Lagrangian case, $L=\text{kinetic energy} - V(x)$ usually where kinetic energy = $m/2 dx/dt dx/dt$.

In (3), it is argued that $dx/dt dx/dt$ is of the form of a Fisher's information with $P(t) = x(t)x(t)$. For the sake of argument, let us consider this to be true. From this it seems to follow in the literature (1), (2), that one may consider instead a $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ with d/dx being the derivative used. Fisher's extremization with $V(x) W(x)W(x)$ as a constraint, or a different constraint, is immediately used, with the notion being that Fisher's information extremization subject to constraints is the fundamental underlying idea of the problem.

We argue that this approach for $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ must be consistent with the $dx/dt dx/dt$ approach i.e. with conservation of energy. The notion of conservation of energy cannot simply disappear in the $dW/dx dW/dx$ Fisher' information scheme given that $V(x)$, the potential, is used. Fisher's information extremization associated with $dW/dx dW/dx$ is: $-d/dx dW/dx$, but this must represent $\langle pp \rangle$. Nonrelativistically this is linked to kinetic energy, but relativistically it would be pp . Nonrelativistically then:

$dx/dt dx/dt C1$ (from the Lagrangian differential equation which is then integrated to create a conservation of energy equation)

$$= C_2 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \quad ((2))$$

Thus without performing any specific extremization of $\frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ or $P \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P)$ with constraints as done in (1) and (2), we already have the relationship ((2)).

$$\text{Thus nonrelativistically: } -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = \langle pp \rangle \quad ((3))$$

This means that: $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} = pp W$ ((4)) for a free particle (where there is no average).

((4)) may be solved to yield: $W = \exp(ipx)$. Thus one already has the free particle solution.

This solution is identical to the eigenfunction of the translation operator multiplied by $-i$ i.e.

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Even if the energy equation $E = pp/2m$ follows from the extremization of the Lagrangian (which (3) argues is identical to the extremization of Fisher's information $\frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt}$ subject to constraints) no Fisher information extremization is needed to write $\exp(ipx)$.

What does one do in the case of a potential? One may create an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which is guaranteed to satisfy a conservation of energy equation. Thus again, there is no need to formulate Fisher's information in terms of $\frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$ or $P \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P)$ and introduce various constraints. $\exp(ip)$ for a free particle, an ensemble and conservation of energy are all that are needed. This is the main point we wish to make.

We next review the approaches of (1) and (2) and try to point out the issues we have.

P(x)=W(x)W(x) from (1)

In (1), $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ is used a priori in a Fisher's information formula:

$$\text{Fisher' information} = C_1 \int dx P(x) \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P(x)) \right\}$$

$$= C_1 \int dx \frac{dW}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \quad ((6))$$

Fisher's information is then extremized subject to the constraints $\int P(x) dx = 1$ and $V(x)P(x)$. This immediately excludes the free particle case because its $P(x)=\text{constant}$, but the free particle is a key physical situation.

The extremization of Fisher's information with constraints yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation, but this equation allows the free particle solution $\exp(ipx)$.

Fisher's Information Extremization with Hamilton-Jacobi Theory and the Continuity Equation (2)

The analysis in (2) is a little more complex, but ultimately Fisher's information is extremized, but with different constraints. In (2), $P(x)$ is used throughout and then at the end of the analysis it is suggested that one define a function $W(x)$ such that:

$$W(x) = \sqrt{P(x)} \exp(iS/\hbar) \text{ where } S \text{ is the classical action} = \int dt \text{ Lagrangian} \quad ((7))$$

The issue we have is that for a free particle $P(x)=1$ and $W(x) = \text{constant} \exp(iS/\hbar)$ where:

$$S = -Et + px \quad ((8))$$

(Note: one may show that $\frac{1}{2}mv^2$ for a free particle is equivalent to $(-Et + px)$ using $v = x/t$.)

Thus the definition is the solution for a free particle i.e. $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. One cannot, however, define the solution to a problem. The extremization equations which are obtained, namely the continuity equation and a second equation yield 0 and conservation of energy respectively for the free particle. Conservation of energy, however, is already known. Thus for the free particle, $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ is defined and an equation equivalent to conservation of energy is proposed when this is known from Newtonian mechanics. For the case of $V(x)$, one may use an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and conservation of energy again.

For completeness, we outline the approach of (2). The quantity to extremize is given as:

$$I = \int dx dt \left\{ \frac{2}{\hbar} P(x) \left[\frac{dS}{dt} \text{ partial} + \frac{1}{2m} \frac{dS}{dx} \frac{dS}{dx} + V \right] + \frac{\hbar}{4m} P \left(\frac{d}{dx} \ln P \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \ln P \right) \right\} \quad ((9))$$

. One may see Hamilton-Jacobi theory present in ((9)). Variation with respect to S yields the continuity equation:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} \text{ partial} + \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ P \frac{dS}{dx} \right\} = 0 \quad ((10))$$

while variation with respect to P yields:

$$\frac{dS}{dt} \text{ partial} + \frac{1}{2m} \frac{dS}{dx} \frac{dS}{dx} + V - \frac{\hbar}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \sqrt{P} \right) / \sqrt{P} = 0 \quad ((11))$$

It is stated that defining $W(x) = \sqrt{P(x)} \exp(iS/\hbar)$ ((13)) and using ((10)) and ((11)) yields the Schrodinger equation. We argue, however, that ((13)) for a free particle yields $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ so $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$ is the momentum operator and $E = p^2/2m$. One may immediately create an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$, calculate an average kinetic energy and use it in a conservation of energy equation. We argue that this should be guaranteed to be equivalent to any result from a Fisher's extremization. Thus we suggest that the final result, namely the Schrodinger equation, is already anticipated by ((6)) or by the solution $\exp(ipx)$ (eigenfunction of $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx}$, an ensemble and conservation of energy).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the literature it is suggested that extremization of Fisher's information is a fundamental idea, governing how physical systems behave (in certain situations). In particular, in (3) it is suggested that the Lagrangian extremization $L = \int dx \dot{x} - V$ is linked to Fisher's information extremization with $C_1 \int dt \dot{x} \dot{x}$ being Fisher's information. We argue that following this result, there seems to be a tendency to consider systems with $P(x)$ and d/dx , the derivative, write a Fisher's information, $\int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \{d/dx \ln(P)\}$ and to extremize it subject to constraints.

We argue that a conservation of energy equation (which follows from the Lagrangian approach or $\int dx \dot{x} \dot{x}$ Fisher's extremization) must still hold a priori. This begs the question: Why is a conservation of energy equation not written down immediately instead of using a variational one? Furthermore, for $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$, Fisher's information becomes $dW/dx dW/dx$ so its extremization yields a nonrelativistic kinetic energy of the form $C_1 d/dx dW/dx / W$. For a free particle, this automatically yields $W = C \exp(ipx)$. For a potential, one may create an ensemble $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ from which one may create an average kinetic energy $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ and use this in a conservation of energy equation $KE(x) + V(x) = E$, thus bypassing and Fisher's information extremization.

We consider two Fisher constrained extremizations appearing in the literature. In one scenario (1), $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ is used which excludes the free particle case, but yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation, which allows the free particle solution $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. The second scenario begins with a $P(x)$ and extremizes Fisher's information with constraints linked to Hamilton-Jacobi theory. The authors then define a function: $W(x) = \sqrt{P(x)} \exp(iS/\hbar)$ where S is the classical action. For a free particle, this definition is $W(x) = \exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Thus the definition is actually the solution for the free particle case, meaning nothing has been derived. From the free particle solution, creating an ensemble and using conservation of energy yields the Schrodinger equation, bypassing extremization of Fisher's information.

In short, in the $dW/dx dW/dx$ type Fisher's information case, the extremization solution must be equivalent to a conservation of energy equation, so we suggest that this equation be written a priori. Furthermore, one must also account for a free particle solution. Extremization cannot bypass this solution.

References

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